

Analysis of Income for Laying Hen Farming Business in Puncak Harapan Village, Enrekang Regency

Musnaim^{1*}, Angga Nugraha², Musdalifah Mansur³

Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidenreng Rappang

Corresponding Author: Musnaim musnaimnaim29@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the income of the laying hen farming business in Puncak Harapan Village, Enrekang Regency. The research population was 30 purebred chicken breeders and a sample of 30 respondents. The sampling technique in this research is in accordance with the statement of Gay and Diehl (1992). The data collection techniques applied in the research are observation, questionnaires or questionnaires. The results of the research can be concluded that the income of the laying hen farming business in Puncak Harapan Village is influenced by several factors such as chicken population, education and work experience. Livestock business income based on scale size is calculated by total revenue minus total costs equal to monthly profit or income. Total income for scale 1 farm with a population of 3000-5000 is IDR 94,850,000, scale 2 with a population of 5000-10,000 is IDR 123,695,000 and scale 3 with a population of 10,000-30,000 is IDR 291,045,000.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a conscious and planned effort to create an atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religion. The development of the livestock sector in realizing the livestock development program operationally begins with regional planning through a systems approach and agribusiness efforts. The development of livestock-based agribusiness areas is an alternative breakthrough program that is expected to answer the challenges and demands of livestock development to increase community income and welfare (Kasim, 2011). Livestock development in Indonesia has bright prospects in the future, this is due to the large population so that mathematically the demand for livestock products such as meat, eggs and milk will also increase. One of the livestock sub-sectors that plays a role in providing animal protein is the poultry sector. Eggs are one of the most nutritionally complete animal foods (Suprijatna 2008).

Everything in a livestock business must be looked at holistically, including financial matters. Finance cannot be seen only from the cost side or from the results side alone, both must be seen in an integrated manner. This has been reflected in the discussion of revenue, income and profits in relation to costs. However, it cannot be known that the results obtained actually reflect livestock efficiency (Sutрино 2007). The production and development of laying hens is expected to be able to meet domestic production requirements and obtain multi-functional benefits from the business unit, which, among other things, can optimize farmer working hours, overcome the problem of unemployment due to limited land ownership and can be used as a part-time business unit (Johan, Bastian 2015).

Income in the livestock business is the most important thing in running a livestock business, however there are several things that can influence the income of breeders such as population size, level of education and experience possessed by the breeder himself, this can influence the size and size of the income earned by the breeder per month. . Based on this description, this is what caused the researcher to carry out this research, with the title "Income analysis of egg-laying breeds of chickens in Puncak Harapan village, Enrekang Regency" to find out how much income is earned on egg-laying breeds of chickens in Puncak Harapan village, Enrekang Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Broadly speaking, egg-laying chicken farming is everything related to production related to maintenance, market sales process, business procurement and the environment where egg-laying chickens are kept starting from the seed phase to the layer phase which will then experience the product production period. The main thing obtained from the laying chicken farming business is eggs, while the meat is a by-product which is rejected chickens (Istikomah, 2018).

Laying chickens are chickens that can be cultivated to obtain the final result in the form of eggs. Laying chickens come from wild chickens which are then raised specifically to produce lots of eggs. In the 1900s, these wild chickens entered rural areas and then in the 1940s, people only got to know other

chickens besides wild chickens, namely Dutch chickens (when the Dutch colonized Indonesia) with special wild chickens from Indonesia which were then called local chickens or native chicken because the location of the native chicken is in the countryside. Meanwhile, Dutch chickens are called foreign chickens or domestic chickens (Chicken breeds) (Suprijatna, 2008).

Laying breeds of chickens are chickens whose eggs can be used to carry out a business to meet standards that can be used as a method production capable of producing large numbers of eggs. Laying chickens are characterized by agile behavior, have rapid sexual maturity, are easily startled, and have relatively small and thin bodies. There are several strains of laying hens in Indonesia, namely Isa brown, Shaver starcross, Cobb, Hysex brown, Babcock and Ross brown (Feri, 2019).

METHODS

Study This done in Kaluppang Village, Maiwa District, Enrekang Regency. This research Study This done on month March until April which is held in the Village Peak Hope Regency Enrekang . Election place done in a way on purpose Because a number of reason among them that is location farm more near with place stay so that can with easy For reachable . Besides That breeders in the village _ Peak Hope part big own eye livelihood as breeders who own population chicken race enough laying _ a lot . The population used in this research were all laying hen breeders in Puncak Harapan Village, Enrekang Regency, totaling 30 laying hen breeders. The sampling technique is based on Sugiyono (2016: 85) by determining the sample using a saturated sample where the sampling technique is that the entire population is used as a sample, so the sample size used is 30 subjects.verification at the place where the research is carried out, in this case the laying hen farm in Puncak Harapan Village, Enrekang Regency.

Interview, is a technique for collecting data using consultations with several laying hen keepers who were used as research respondents related to the laying hen business. To make it easier for respondents to understand the interview, the researcher used a questionnaire which contained a list of questions which were then arranged according to the researcher's needs and abilities, such as the income obtained, costs, the process of raising laying hens, the identity of the breeder and so on.

Observed Variables

The variables that will be observed include: Fixed costs include cage and seedling costs (DOC). Variable costs include feed, medicine, labor, electricity and water, cage equipment and transportation. Among other things, income is the sale of eggs, sale of finished chickens and sale of feces. Income includes profits.

Data Analysis Method

The primary data or secondary data obtained will then be used as learning material in this research. This research data processing and analysis uses quantitative research

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Puncak Harapan Village is located in Maiwa District, Enrekang Regency, South Sulawesi. Puncak Harapan Village is one of 21 villages in the Maiwa District area, which is located ± 7 km to the north of the District Capital, ± 40 km to the east of the Regency capital, and ± 208 km to the north of the Provincial capital. Puncak Harapan Village has an area of ± 14.08 KM² or $\pm 1,408$ Ha. The administrative boundaries of Puncak Harapan Village are:

State of the Population

The population condition is a description of the population of a region, both quantitatively and qualitatively, which can be used as a basis for developing a region in the context of development so that it is right on target. The population condition is described by the number of residents based on gender in an area. We can see that the total population in Puncak Harapan Village, Enrekang Regency is 924 people. Where the population of men and women is almost the same, where the male population is 470 people and the female population is 454 people. The existing population is one source of labor in the livestock business. Potential of Breeders in Puncak Harapan Village, Enrekang Regency Puncak Hrapan Village, located in Enrekang Regency, is one of the regions in Indonesia that has great potential in the livestock sector. This potential has become a concern for society, government and agricultural experts. With geographical conditions and abundant natural resources, Puncak Harapan Village offers various opportunities for the development of sustainable livestock businesses.

Based on table on so potency breeders in the village Peak Hope more dominate breeder chicken race with number 240,600 head . Temporary breeder cow cut 237 heads . Livelihood __ residents of i Puncak Harapan Village is mostly in the sector agriculture. However, many residents have started laying chicken farming businesses. This business opens up employment opportunities for people who have dropped out of school or work part time while still in school.

Characteristics Respondent

Each household or farmer has its own characteristics Which different Which can describe circumstances respondents. As for several elements of data collected, namely the name and age of the respondent, level education, farming experience, main and side jobs and amount population cattle chicken laying breeds. Age Respondent. One of the factors that supports a business being able to run is age factor. Someone who is younger usually tends to be more Have an optimistic nature in taking on new challenges compared with older age. This is because physical aging begins to occur decreases and it will usually be difficult to generate new ideas. But deep running a business, for example in the field of

animal husbandry, that age Relatively young is not a guarantee that a business that will be run will experience success success.

Based on data results study on table 5 obtained that age respondents Which most Lots do business farm purebred chicken laying are 25-30 years old, namely 10 people while the fewest are those aged 51-55 years, namely only 2 people. This is in accordance with Dewanti's opinion (2012), which states that the number of village residents shared become 2 group, that is 1) resident age 0-14 year or called population by age Which unproductive and 2) population aged 15-65 years or called resident productive. This is also reinforced by Fatati's opinion (2001), that the younger a person is, the more quickly accept changes in the surrounding environment, this is caused by farmers Young people are more likely to have a lot of potential for development to increase knowledge and skills in the sustainability process his business.

Level Education Respondent

Education has an important role in carrying out a business Where education is means Which can support knowledge, Skills And character or personality Which owned by somebody. With exists education para breeder capable develop creativity in carry out a business, especially in the field of animal husbandry. Following are the results data research by level education chicken farmer laying breeds.

Percentage of education level of laying hen breeders located in Village Peak Hope , namely the highest level of education 40% of junior high school graduates and 30% of elementary school graduates. Whereas The lowest level of education is for high school graduates, namely 23% and Higher education as much as 7%. This is in accordance with the conditions in In today's society, in general, some people's farms are partial big own level education junior high school to lower. Matter This since with opinion of Risqina (2011), who believes that education plays a role important in influencing a person's mindset in matters determining decisions and management arrangements in running a business will be implemented in the future. This is also reinforced by Hero's opinion (2017), which states that breeders have a higher level of education high speed in receiving or understanding information and ideas new compared to with Which own level education more low so that they more capable create innovation new in in terms of developing his farm. However, farming experience too play an important role and contribute to the success of a particular business in chicken farming sector laying breeds.

Experience Breeding

Breeding experience is related to a person's level of experience in running a livestock business. Taking a long time to breed is wrong one factor that a breeder wants to have because of its existence farming experience, then a person can easily do it livestock business starting from the maintenance process, marketing and existence experience raising can guarantee success something business

Table 1. Characteristics Respondent Breeder Chicken Race Laying Based on Experience Breeding in Village Peak Hope Subdistrict Maiwa

No	Experience Breeding (Year)	Frequency (Person)	Percentage (%)
1	2-4	9	30
2	5-7	17	57
3	8-10	4	13
Amount		30	100

Source: Data Primary Which has processed , 2023

Based on data Which obtained on table 7 can is known that Most respondents have farming experience, namely 5-7 years amount breeder as much 17 person with percentage 57%, Then in The medium level is 2-4 years with a total of 9 breeders with percentage 30% And in level final is at on breeder Which own experience during 8-10 year that is as much 4 person with percentage 13%. This is in accordance with the opinion of Nitisemito and Burhan (2004), Which state that If the more long do something business so will , increasingly Lots also experience Which will obtained in field Which pursued the.

Results Analysis Income Income Farm Chicken Race Laying

Following data Farm chicken race Laying in Village Peak Hope Subdistrict Maiwa based on division scale.

Table 2. Data Respondent Breeder Chicken Race Laying based on Scale in Village Peak hope Subdistrict Maiwa

Information	Scale 1	Scale 2	Scale 3
Total Population Chicken Race Laying (Tail)	3000-5000	5500 - 10000	15000 - 30000
Amount Breeder	3	23	4
Average Production Eggs/grains/day	4,754	7,600	23,473
Marketing	Collector	Collector	Collector

Source: Data Primary Which has processed, 2023

Based on data Which obtained on table 1 that is breeder Which raising laying hens in Puncak Hrapan Village that is as much 30 person Which each breeder the divided into 3 scales based on the smallest, middle and largest populations. Based on the results obtained on Scale 1, there is a population of laying hens namely 3000-5000 heads with a total of 3 breeders, Scale 2 as many as 5000-10000 heads with a total of 23 breeders and Scale 3 as many as 10,000-30,000 laying hens with a total of 4 breeders person. The population of laying hens on each farm is different, this is the case because there are breeders who are just starting a business and there are also breeders who has been running a

laying chicken farming business for many years years and still persists today. Next for average production The eggs produced by each farm are different on a scale of 1 average the average egg production of laying hens is 4,754 eggs/day, Scale 2 is 7,600 eggs/day and Scale 3 is 23,473 eggs/head, which is then the third scale the market their eggs with how to sell to collector.

Cost Production

Production costs are divided into 2, namely fixed costs are costs will not change even if the amount issued is greater than the amount production whereas cost No still is cost Which can fickle along with walking time. Before start something business farm In laying hens there are several things that must be considered, one of which is is with expenditure capital. Capital is something expenditure goods carried out to obtain profits in carrying out a business. Capital can be divided into 2, namely fixed capital and non-fixed capital. Following Table of capital production costs for laying egg-laying chicken farms in the village Peak .Based on the research results in table 3, it can be concluded that costs still the most issued is on Scale 3 farms, namely with fixed costs of IDR 130,625,000 consists of land tax costs making cages and seeds with variable costs of Rp. 564,737,000 _ Which consisting of medicines and vitamins, cage equipment, labor costs, feed, water and electricity and transportation. Meanwhile costs the lowest there is on Scale 1, namely with a fixed cost of Rp. 130,625,000 _ at cost variable amounting to Rp. 107,250 ,000 This is due to electricity and water costs issued on each scale is different and is followed by the amount different populations of laying hens. This is in accordance with Hero's opinion (2017), Which say that capital in operate business farm Laying chicken breeds are divided into 2, namely fixed capital and non-fixed capital. Fixed capital is capital consisting of land and building taxes, seeds and cages while non-fixed capital consists of feed, electricity, labor, medicines medicines and vaccines etc. This is also reinforced by the opinion of Soekartawi (2008) that capital is something needs Which must issued And can used in the do something business in process production. Capital divided into 2 types based on the source, namely self-issued capital and capital foreign or loan. Then based on ownership, capital divided become 2, that is capital individual and community capital.

Reception

Revenue is the proceeds obtained from the sale of goods from a business carried out so that this revenue can only be calculated by using value. Following table cost reception from farm chicken race laying eggs in the Village Peak Hope Subdistrict Maiwa.

Table 3. Total Reception Farm Chicken Race Laying based on Scale in the Village Peak Hope Subdistrict Maiwa

Information	Scale 1 (Rp)	Scale 2 (Rp)	Scale 3 (Rp)
Sale egg	228,160,000	550,500,000	1,126,620,000
Chicken reject	-	-	-
Dirt (Fertilizer)	7,833,000	23.0 00,000	38 000 000
Total Reception	235,993,000	573,500 ,000	1,164.62 0,000

Source: Data Primary Which has processed, 2023

Based on table 3 above, the results obtained show that the number of receipts most Lots there is on Scale 3 Which amount Rp. 1,164.62 0,000 Which includes egg sales for 1 month with population as much as 10000-30000 tail chicken laying with price as big as Rp.1. 126.62 0,000 and sales of compost fertilizer amounting to Rp. 3 8,000,000. Then reception the most furthermore there is on Scale 2 that is as much as Rp. 573. 5 0 0,000 with total sales of chicken eggs for 1 month, namely u as much Rp. 550,500,000 with population 5000-10000, And sales of compost fertilizer amounting to Rp. 23 000 000. As for reception Which most A little there is on Scale 1 that is as much Rp. 235 . 993 000 with population chicken race laying as much 300 0 - 5000 tail. Total sale egg on Scale 1 This as much Rp. 228,160,000 during 1 month, And sale fertilizer compost as big as Rp. 7,833 ,000. Matter This in accordance with opinion Dewanti And Sihombing (2012), which states that acceptance in the livestock business chicken is the result of the sale of all products received. Reception only calculated in cash and then received by the farmer Then can is known in form reception. Matter This Also strengthened with the opinion of Dewi, et al (2018) that the acceptance obtained subsequently will be used to cover total costs which has been issued. Reception This includes selling eggs, selling rejected chickens and selling droppings chicken which is then processed into compost.

Income

Income is the result received from an existing business carried out by taking into account the costs that have been incurred. For more details regarding the income earned by breeders laying hens in Puncak Harapan Village, Enrekang Regency can seen on table following. Based on results Which obtained on table 10 on, obtained profit Which most big that is there is on Scale 3 that is as big as Rp. 599,883,000 , this is due to population factors on Scale 3 at the most Lots compared to with Scale 1 (Rp. 110,493,000) or Scale 2 (Rp. 339,048,000). This shows the difference in profits obtained at each laying hen farm in Puncak Harapan Village, where this is influenced by each production costs incurred both in terms of fixed costs and variable costs. Matter This related with opinion Hero (2017), Which say that income in business cultivation farm chicken laying obtained from subtraction of total revenue from the total cost of fixed costs and fees variable. Matter This strengthened also with opinion Nirvana (2003), Which state that income can influenced by various factors, including the scale of the business, the efficiency of using labor in the business

livestock, production produced (in the form of eggs, chickens rejection and sale manure used as fertilizer), the amount of capital spent.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Farm chicken race laying Which there is in Puncak Harapan Village with a total of 30 farms with Different populations start from a population of 3000-5000 individuals which are then divided into 3 scales to make calculations easier. As for income from of these three scales, the one that produces the most profit is obtained namely at Scale 3, then followed by livestock at Scale 2 and farms that produce the least profit are found on the Difference Scale the caused Because amount population from each farm different as well as production costs Which issued is different.

Based on the results and discussion of research in the field, the author intends to provide suggestions which hopefully can provide benefits for future researchers as well as the government and society, namely as follows:

For Researcher Expected Next

For study more stout source nor related references degan level income breeder chicken race layers for results his research can more good.

For Government

For government expected capable build effective coordination , good _ between farm chicken race laying . Effective coordination _ can push happen cohesiveness so that 's expected breeder chicken race laying can mingle in accordance with policies that have been planned.

For Community

For community (breeders) In develop business breeder chicken race layers can use alternative strategies from the results of this research as reference material in developing income breeder chicken race laying .

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Analysis of Income for Laying Hen Farming Business in Puncak Harapan Village, Enrekang Regency."

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